

Deliverable D1.3

Project management handbook with templates & guide (first update)

Date – 03/02/2025
Deadline – 31/01/2025

Claire HOUZÉ

ZORLUENERJI

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Document Control Sheet

PROJECT INFORMATION

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Coordinator	CEA - Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives		

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Task Leader (Name and Short Org. Name)	Claire HOUZÉ (CEA)
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1.0	29/01/2025	Claire HOUZÉ (CEA)	First version
2.0	03/02/2025	SPI	Feedback for exploitation

Document Review

Reviewer	Date	Reviewer Name (Short Organisation Name)
Work Package leader	30/01/2025	Claire HOUZÉ (CEA)
Project Manager	30/01/2025	Claire HOUZÉ (CEA)
Exploitation Manager	03/02/2025	Ana Fernandes (CEA)
Coordinator	30/01/2025	Elie GHANATOS (CEA)

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ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition
GA	General Assembly
PSC	Project Steering Committee
AB	Advisory Board
WPL	Work Package Leaders
WP	Work Package

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1. About the project

SEHRENE's new electrothermal energy storage (ETES) concept is designed to store renewable electricity (RE) and heat and to reconstitute it as needed. It is very energy-efficient (80-85%), is geographically independent and uses no critical raw materials. It enables 8-12 times longer storage duration than Li-ion, with LCOS of 80 – 137 €/MWh, depending on the use-case. This is lower than pumped hydro, the lowest-cost commercial electricity storage. Its lifetime of 20-30 years is 2 – 3x longer than Li-ion. A TRL4 prototype and the digital twins of 3 full use-cases will be delivered: (i) ceramics plant storing excess, on-site PV power in a micro-grid and industrial waste-heat for continuous green H₂ production and self-consumption, (ii) a smart-grid, and (iii) a geothermal power plant. The ETES integrates: (i) a novel heat-pump design with a coefficient of performance of 50% the theoretical maximum, (ii) a novel thermal energy storage system with energy density of 90 kWh/m³ (+30%), containing phase-change material in a novel metallic Kelvin cells-like foam and (iii) ORC with novel operating parameters. New digital tools will optimise the energy management of the storage and facilitate investment decisions by potential end-users taking LCA and techno-economic factors into account. SEHRENE unites 5 R&D teams with top-level expertise in prototyping, physics-based modelling, characterisation and digital twins of thermo-electric systems, thermal storage and AI-based energy-management; 1 RE producer, 1 DSO, 1 ceramics company, 1 SME developing decision-support tools, and 1 SME for dissemination and communication. The exploitation plan aims to implement the solution in the first factory in 2029. SEHRENE's market penetration will enable to capture 1% of the market by 2040 avoiding 90Mm³ of NG and 15Mt CO₂/year. R&D and industrial partners project to generate 5.8M€ in revenues by 2035 from sales of heat pumps, thermal storage, ORC, licenses to R&D results and consulting services.

In summary, SEHRENE introduces an innovative Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) solution, addressing a critical technological challenge faced by conventional ETES systems - round-trip efficiencies diminished by temperature losses. This disruptive architecture not only resolves this issue but also positions itself as a viable option to meet Europe's energy transition requirements.

Consortium

Commissariat à L'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA)
 University of Liège (ULIÈGE)
 Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI)
 Turboden (TURBODEN)
 Fundación Circe Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE)
 Torrecid SA (TORRECID)
 Zorlu Enerji Elektrik Üretim AS (ZOREN)
 Cuerva Energia SLU (CUERVA)
 Sociedade Portuguesa de Inovação (SPI)
 Technovative Solutions Ltd (TVS)
 University of Leicester (ULEIC)

2. Executive Summary

Proper project management is a keystone to a successful project progress and leads to the fulfilment of its goals. A challenging project like SEHRENE requires an effective, efficient and well-defined management scheme. It must ensure a flawless flow of research and knowledge between the various Work Packages. It has to provide mechanisms to make decisions that will affect the project's outcome as well as administrative, technical and scientific coordination of the project. Moreover, it is responsible for the effective dissemination of the tasks achieved during the project and helps to select the most appropriate exploitation routes for the generated know-how.

This document describes the project management and quality assurance scheme, which will be followed during the project in order to smoothly achieve its objectives. The setting will be reflected and could be modified in the future if another approach would seem more efficient.

3. Introduction

The current deliverable is part of the task 1.2 – Operational Management. The content of this document is based on and in line with the project management and implementation setting described in the Annex I of the project's Grant Agreement (Description of the Action, DoA) and the project's Consortium Agreement (CA).

The purpose of this document is to describe the proposed project management, procedures and quality assurance scheme, which will be followed during the project to achieve its objectives. It will ensure a flawless flow of research and knowledge between various Work Packages (WPs) and provide mechanisms to take decisions that will affect the project's outcome as well as administrative, technical and scientific coordination of the project. Moreover, the defined structure will ensure the effective dissemination of the tasks achieved during the project and will help to select the most appropriate exploitation routes for the generated know-how.

4. Consortium organizational structure and roles in the project

The consortium organization is described below and depicted in Figure 1.

Figure 1 Organigram of the consortium.

4.1 Project Coordinator

The Project Coordinator (Elie GHANATOS, from CEA) is responsible for overall coordination activities and technical monitoring of the project. The Project Manager, Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and the General Assembly (GA), are assisting him in this management task. He follows the project throughout its whole lifecycle, on a day-to-day basis. He gathers the necessary information for efficient communication both with the Commission (activity, financial and final reports, audits, etc.) and within the consortium (consortium and AB meetings, schedules, reports, progress reports, etc.). In case any major problem arises, he has the possibility to call for an extraordinary meeting of the General Assembly or for a full meeting of the partners. The Project Coordinator communicates with the Commission on behalf of the whole consortium. He is also responsible for distribution of the financial support amongst the partners paid by the Commission.

4.2 Project Manager

The main role of a Project Manager (Claire HOUZÉ from CEA) is to support the Project Coordinator and WP Leaders in their administrative, financial, and communication roles. She takes care of project amendments, monitoring and timing of technical deliverables and milestones, timely and quality reporting,

checking the partners' budget follow-up (e.g. preparing and checking cost statements, distribution of funding, etc.). The Project Manager is responsible for proper information flow between the GA and Coordinator on one side and WP Leaders and partners on the other (decisions taken, to-do lists, deadlines, minutes of meetings – for template see Appendix B). Furthermore, the Project Manager coordinates project meetings: PSC meetings, 6-monthly meeting and official review meetings.

4.3 Work Package Leaders (WPLs) and Project Steering Committee (PSC)

The structure of the work plan is divided into 7 Work Packages (WPs) and for each Work Package there is a Work Package Leader (WPL) nominated. WPLs are responsible for controlling the progress of the scheduled work within the WP in terms of technical achievement, planned deliverables and expenses and for informing the General Assembly and other WPLs about a project progress. Other tasks of WPLs are as follows:

- To collect the information (technical, programmatic) needed to prepare periodic progress reports and to transmit them to the Project Coordinator.
- To transmit information from the Project Coordinator to the partners involved in the Work Package.
- To manage topic-oriented meetings and to report to the Project Coordinator on all matters related to the topic (planning, costs, etc.).
- To allow a fluid upstream and downstream exchange of information, regular contact is being kept between the Project Coordinator, Project Manager and WP Leaders.

All Work Package Leaders form a Project Steering Committee (PSC), which acts as a managerial decision-making body for the project and is responsible for supporting the Project Coordinator. Details of the SEHRENE's PSC located in Table 1. In the event of technological changes that cannot be addressed directly by WP Leaders, the PSC will investigate and advise appropriate actions. The WP Leaders will implement the actions. PSC takes decisions in those cases where it is not necessary to refer to the General Assembly. A consensus will be aimed to be reached wherever possible. If consensus cannot be reached, decisions are being taken after a simple majority vote. PSC meets at least two times per year to perform internal assessment of the project and assure the conformity and the quality of all project deliverables with the requirements. Quarterly teleconferences are scheduled, this can be amended depending on the project progress or issues. Other partner teleconferences and exclusive partner workshop meetings are encouraged.

Table 1: List of SEHRENE Work Package Leaders and members of the Project Steering Committee.

WP	WP name	WP Leader	Partner
1	Project Management and Coordination	Elie GHANATOS	CEA
2	Requirement analysis	Tugrul HAZARD	ZORLU

3	Integrated ETES conception and modelling	Vincent LEMORT	ULIEGE
4	Prototyping SEHRENE ETES concept	Benedicte CHAMPEL	CEA
5	System optimization for the use cases	Paola BOMBARDA	POLIMI
6	System optimization for the use cases	Mahfuza AHMED	TVS
7	Dissemination, communication and exploitation	Ana FERNANDES	SPI

4.4 Task leaders

The work to be implemented in each Work Package is divided into tasks. Every task is being managed by a Task Leader who is responsible for carrying out the work planned in the task. Task Leaders communicate with their respective Work Package Leaders on a regular basis. They provide inputs for project progress report drafting. The list of all tasks is part of DoA.

4.5 Dissemination manager

As several dissemination activities are planned to be undertaken during the project lifetime, a role of a Dissemination Manager (WP7 Leader, Ana FERNANDES, SPI) has been established. Regular contact with all Work Package Leaders will ensure timely communication and dissemination of project outcomes and results. The aim of the dissemination activities is to inform the specialized research community but also recognized sub-system providers, integrators and end-users about the latest achievements in the relevant field; and to allow the consortium to reinforce the links between the European R&D communities and end-users clustered around other European or national research activities.

4.6 Exploitation manager

The role of an Exploitation and Innovation Manager (Ana FERNANDES, SPI) has been set to continuously monitor the developed key Exploitable Results and then assess the market potential of the developed know-how. The data extraction of market characteristics and determination of the actual market trends is imperative to realize the full commercial potential of the project results. Therefore, the exploitation manager will lead the work on market analysis survey and benchmarking activity, including preparation of exploitation plans (performed individually by all industrial partners). Potential users outside the consortium will be identified and the Exploitation Manager will serve as the main contact point for business related issues (together with the PSC and GA).

4.7 General assembly

The General Assembly (GA) is a decision-making consortium body at the strategic level which was established at the beginning of the project. It consists of key senior representatives from each partner

organization or their proxies (e.g. WPLs). It acts and makes decisions in line with what is stated in the Consortium Agreement and DoA.

The tasks of the GA are as follows:

- Responsibility for project strategy and its exploitation.
- Monitoring of project progress, its achievements and costs.
- Supervision of technical developments.
- Coordination of dissemination actions and exploitation activities.
- Making agreements on contract changes if required (budgets, resources, plans, etc.).
- Solving problems with a potential impact on project strategies, resources and objectives, defining the necessary contingency plans.
- Keeping track of medium- and long-term objectives.

GA meets at least once a year and is chaired by the coordinator who is assisted by the Project Manager. Minutes of the GA will be distributed to the consortium and the Project Officer, it will also remain available on SEHRENE collaborative platform (Collab i2i).

4.8 Advisory Board

The User Advisory Board will be established for delivering strategic advice needed during the main project periods. The main role of the Advisory Board (AB) is as follows:

- To ensure objective decisions of the General Assembly during the technical specification phase at the start of the project, validation of results and to confirm the continuity of high-quality objectives before mid-term and support for flawless result exploitation and shift towards potentially new innovative products at the end of the project.
- To increase Pan-European concept of the project.
- To provide desirable feedback from other closely related European or national activities in high temperature thermal energy storage or heat storage applications for industrial processes and thus to provide synergy with European R&D and industrialisation.

The following stakeholders agreed on being members of SEHRENE's AB:

- UGITECH,
- Baikowski,
- ENGIE,
- Region AURA,
- Geothermal Energy Association

The experts will be identified in coordination with the partners.

A Non-Disclosure Agreement (NDA) will be signed with the AB members. AB should meet at least once a year with the General Assembly. AB minutes will be then distributed to AB and consortium members and to Project Officer.

Partners will be able to act openly towards the AB members, since they will be bound by the NDA.

5. Internal Management Procedure

The following procedures will ensure smooth implementation of the project and timely awareness and reaction to potential problems.

5.1 Communication

To make easier the communication within the main consortium bodies, the following mailing list has been set up:

- coordination@sehrene.eu

Other mailing lists for a specific WP or for the PSC will be set up on request. Appendix A (see 7.1) features a table of contact details with current status. It will be regularly updated and available to partners on the project's file repository (Collab i2i).

In order to share files and documents related to the project, the Collab i2i platform will be used. SEHRENE project webpage will provide easily accessible information for the public. It will be updated on a regular basis and will act as a management tool. A mailing list : info@sehrene.eu will be used for external communication such as newsletters, invitation to SEHRENE events/activities.

5.2 Decision making

It can be expected that most of the decisions will be taken by consensus of all the partners. In a first step it is the role of the Project Coordinator to identify and possibly resolve potential conflicts in a proactive manner in collaboration with the WPLs. All cases will be discussed among the conflicting parties in good faith. However, in case of a serious conflict, when the Coordinator is unable to mediate between conflicting parties, each partner can ask the General Assembly in writing to organise a conflict resolution meeting. The GA will organise such a meeting within 30 days following reception of the written request and attempts for arbitration will be performed in increasing order of authority from the level of the WPLs to the GA level. Within the meeting, agreements are searched for by dialogue and mutual concession. In case of a failure to find an agreement, the GA will make the final decision. The voting rules are described in the Consortium Agreement.

5.3 Project planning

In order to achieve project's specific objectives, the structure of the work plan is divided into 7 Work Packages (WPs), each targeting different objectives, tasks and expected results.

Description of the Action (DoA) thoroughly describes the project plan and its implementation. The beginning of tasks and scheduled deliverables and milestones are shown in the detailed Gantt Chart (Appendix F, see 7.6). The list of Deliverables and Milestones is available in the DoA.

The linkage and dependencies between the WPs, as well as the PERT diagram between the tasks of each WP, can be found in the Appendix E (see 7.5).

5.4 Progress reporting

Progress made in reaching the deliverables in each Work Package will be regularly assessed by integrating all inputs from the WPLs and Coordinator (PSC). The progress of the project will be assessed at two levels with the help of general indicators, which are the objectives, milestones, deliverables, and the appropriate use of budget, respectively. On top of that a quality control by Exploitation Manager will ensure efficient translation of generated know-how to the commercialized products and services.

All deliverables generated by the people in charge will be checked and controlled in this sequence: WP leader > Project Manager > Exploitation Manager > Coordinator > Submission to EC > EC Project Officer or reviewer), as illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2 Procedure for quality assurance of Deliverables.

The first draft of the report is to be ready approximately one month before the submission date. Complete adherence with deadlines will be required in order to submit deliverables on time. A deliverable template is available for partners in Appendix C. Moreover, the PSC will conduct the internal quality assessment of milestones and deliverables that are based on the quantified objectives detailed in chapter Excellence of DoA and within the WP description. The 6 months periodicity for the PSC meeting, in person and remotely

alternatively, is foreseen to perform internal assessment of the project and ensure the conformity and the quality of all project deliverables with the requirements. The WP Leaders are responsible for monitoring progress in their own WP, to identify risks and to rapidly inform the PSC if any changes regarding the DoA occur.

The internal reporting will consist of financial reporting, person-months (PMs) reporting and technical reporting. The goal of the technical reporting is to give an overview of main activities and results obtained during the last period of the project by individual partners in order to monitor the project development in last 6 months and prepare a summary activity report on the project progress finally compiled per WP. Internal templates will be provided to partners.

The financial and PMs reporting template will be drafted in coming weeks, the scientific reporting template is available in Appendix D. The following scheme is set:

- Every 6 months, internal periodic reporting are planned.
- Official reporting towards the EC in M14, M28 and M42.
- Any changes or problems should always be immediately communicated to the Coordinator and Project Manager.
- Partners will be informed about the reporting deadline 1 month before.

Reporting towards the Commission is scheduled in M14, M28 and M42. The Periodic Report must be submitted within 60 days from the end of the reporting period. It includes the requests for payment and must be drawn up using the forms and templates provided in the electronic exchange system. It is being submitted electronically via the Participant Portal.

The periodic report consists of the following parts:

- Technical event report:
 - Explanation of work carried out with a publishable summary.
 - Overview of progress.
 - Deliverables' check (according to the timetable in the Deliverable list).
- Financial event report:
 - Explanation of the use of resources.
 - Financial statement from each beneficiary and third party.
 - Periodic summary financial statement.

If a partner does not provide the data, the Coordinator can submit the statement without it which means zero costs for the partner concerned.

The Final report which is to be submitted electronically *via* the Participant Portal in M42 consists of:

- Final technical report.
- Overview of the action implementation (template from the Portal Periodic Report)Final financial report:
 - Final financial statement (individual and consolidated, for all beneficiaries and affiliated entities),
 - Explanation of the use of resources,
 - Certificate on the financial statements.

Project risks will be constantly assessed and evaluated within the whole project duration. The methodology to be followed for risk contingency consists of four steps:

- Risk identification: areas of potential risk will be identified and classified.
- Risk evaluation: the probability of events will be determined, and the consequences associated with their occurrence will be examined.
- Risk response: methods will be produced to reduce or control the risk.
- Risk control and report: lessons learnt will be documented.

All risk management issues will be documented in the Periodic Reports.

5.5 Publication procedure

A fair and transparent procedure for the submission of an abstract, paper or other external publication will be implemented, in line both with the GA and the CA. The framework is defined in the Consortium Agreement Article 8.4 Dissemination and is in line with Article 17.4 and Annex 5 of the Grant Agreement.

Prior notice of any planned publication should be given to other consortium members at least 15 calendar days before the publication. Any objection to the planned publication shall be made in accordance with the Grant Agreement in writing to the Coordinator and to the consortium member proposing the dissemination within 15 calendar days after reception of the notice. If no objection is made within the time limit, the publication is permitted (Figure 3).

The following information will be always mentioned in the publication: *“This project has received funding from the European Union’s Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101135763, SEHRENE “.*

Figure 3 Information and timeline of intention of publication.

5.6 Project meetings

As already mentioned above in the respective chapters dedicated to consortium bodies, the General Assembly and User Advisory Board should meet at least once a year, the Project Steering Committee biannually. Moreover, Work Package Leaders will communicate monthly via teleconferences for the first year and at least quarterly from the second year. Other partner teleconferences and exclusive partner workshop meetings are encouraged. If needed, an ad-hoc meeting can be scheduled in order to discuss any relevant issue. To save time and resources, operational meetings could also be performed by using a teleconferencing system, arranged according to the nearest possible availability.

The Project Manager will inform at least 2 months prior the meeting about the agenda and location of the physical meeting. Table 2 shows the SEHRENE management meetings and communication.

Table 2: SEHRENE management meetings and communication.

	Management level				
	GA	EAB	PSC	WPs	Tasks
Annually	physical	physical			
Biannually			physical		
Quarterly			remote		
Monthly				remote	remote

6. Conclusions

The proposed project management, procedures and quality assurance setting will be followed during the whole lifetime of the project in order to smoothly and successfully achieve its objectives. The consortium organizational structures, bodies and roles in the project are set and internal procedures drafted. The scheme will be reflected throughout the project and if needed it could be modified if another approach would be more efficient. For the time being, the SEHRENE consortium believes that the proposed processes will help to reach the project's objectives.

7. Degree of progress

The degree of progress for this deliverable is 100%

8. Appendix

8.1 Appendix A: SEHRENE partners contact details

Name	Email Address
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Ziyi Guo	ziyiguo@spi.pt

8.2 Appendix B: SEHRENE minutes of meeting template

Meeting Minute/Agenda

Insert Event/Meeting Title
Insert Author(s) Name Surname (PARTNER)

Date - Deadline

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2

1. Meeting Chairperson & Facilitators

Chairperson: Insert Name Surname (Organization)
Facilitator(s): Insert Name Surname (Organization) (insert only if applicable)

2. Agenda

- Insert discussion point 1
- Insert discussion point 2
- Insert discussion point 3
- Insert discussion point 4
- Meeting Outcomes and Future Actions

Table 1. Event Schedule/Program (optional)

Time	Title	Speaker/Participants
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum

3. Participants

- WP1: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP2: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP3: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP4: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP5: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP6: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP7: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)
- WP8: Insert Name (Insert Organisation)

3

4. Insert discussion point 1

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing.

4

5. Meeting Outcomes and Upcoming Actions

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting.

Table 2. Upcoming Actions/To do Items

Action Description	Due Date	Responsible Person: Name (Partner)
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum
Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum	Lorem ipsum

Figure 1. Insert figure caption here

RGB	RGB	RGB	RGB
195	34	238	115
32	93	143	178
38	170	36	67

8.3 Appendix C: SEHRENE deliverable template

Deliverable DX.X
Deliverable Title
 Date - Deadline

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Document title here |

Document Control Sheet

PROJECT INFORMATION

Project Number	101135783		
Project Acronym	SEHRENE		
Project Full title	Store Electricity and Heat foR climatE Neutral Europe		
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Coordinator	CEA - Commissariat à l'énergie atomique et aux énergies alternatives		

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Date Approved by Coordinator	

Document title here |

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Legal disclaimer
 This project is funded by the European Union under the Grant Agreement no. 101135783. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or European Climate Infrastructure and Environment Agency (CINEA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document title here |

ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Definition

Document title here |

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1. About the project

SEHRENE's new electrothermal energy storage (ETES) concept is designed to store renewable electricity (RE) and heat and to reconstitute it as needed. It is very energy-efficient (80-85%), is geographically independent and uses no critical raw materials. It enables 8-12 times longer storage duration than Li-ion, with LCOS of 80 – 137 €/MWh, depending on the use-case. This is lower than pumped hydro, the lowest-cost commercial electricity storage. Its lifetime of 20-30 years is 2 – 3x longer than Li-ion. A TRL4 prototype and the digital twins of 3 full use-cases will be delivered: (i) ceramics plant storing excess, on-site PV power in a micro-grid and industrial waste-heat for continuous green H₂ production and self-consumption, (ii) a smart-grid, and (iii) a geothermal power plant. The ETES integrates: (i) a novel heat-pump design with a coefficient of performance of 50% the theoretical maximum, (ii) a novel thermal energy storage system with energy density of 90 kWh/m³ (+30%), containing phase-change material in a novel metallic Kelvin cells-like foam and (iii) ORC with novel operating parameters. New digital tools will optimise the energy management of the storage and facilitate investment decisions by potential end-users taking LCA and technico-economic factors into account. SEHRENE unites 5 R&D teams with top-level expertise in prototyping, physics-based modelling, characterisation and digital twins of thermo-electric systems, thermal storage and AI-based energy-management: 1 RE producer, 1 DSO, 1 ceramics company, 1 SME developing decision-support tools, and 1 SME for dissemination and communication. The exploitation plan aims to implement the solution in the first factory in 2029. SEHRENE's market penetration will enable to capture 1% of the market by 2040 avoiding 90Mm³ of NG and 15Mt CO₂/year. R&D and industrial partners project to generate 5.8M€ in revenues by 2035 from sales of heat pumps, thermal storage, ORC, licenses to R&D results and consulting services.

In summary, SEHRENE introduces an innovative Electro-Thermal Energy Storage (ETES) solution, addressing a critical technological challenge faced by conventional ETES systems - round-trip efficiencies diminished by temperature losses. This disruptive architecture not only resolves this issue but also positions itself as a viable option to meet Europe's energy transition requirements.

Consortium

Commissariat à l'Énergie Atomique et aux Énergies Alternatives (CEA)
 University of Liège (ULIÈGE)
 Politecnico di Milano (POLIMI)
 Turboden (TURBODEN)
 Fundación Circe Centro de Investigación de Recursos y Consumos Energéticos (CIRCE)
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2. Executive Summary

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing.

- Simply dummy text of the printing
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- Simply dummy text of the printing

Document title here |

3. Introduction

Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book. It has survived not only five centuries, but also the leap into electronic typesetting, remaining essentially unchanged. It was popularised in the 1960s with the release of Letraset sheets containing.

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4. Title 1

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Figure 1. Insert figure caption here.

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Table 1. Insert table title here

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Simply dummy text of the printing and typesetting industry. Lorem Ipsum has been the industry's standard dummy text ever since the 1500s, when an unknown printer took a galley of type and scrambled it to make a type specimen book.

Figure 2. Insert figure caption here

8.4 Appendix D: SEHRENE technical reporting template

Project Number	101135763
Project Acronym	SEHRENE
Project Full title	Store Electricity and Heat foR climatE Neutral Europe
RP number	[1], [2], [final]
Dates	from [dd/mm/yyyy] to [dd/mm/yyyy]

No page limit per work-package but the report should be concise and readable. Any duplication should be avoided.

1. Overview of progress	
1.1 Objectives	<p>List the specific objectives for the project as described in section 1.1 of the DoA:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Provide a short summary of progress towards the achievement of each of the project objectives. • Highlight significant activities in support of these achievements. • Report on objectives not fully achieved or not on schedule.
1.2 Explanation of the work carried out per WP	<p>Include a description of how the project has achieved each objective of the period.</p>
WP1	<p>Please provide details by task numbers, fill in, and describe all submitted deliverables. In addition, precise if any Milestone has been passed during the reporting period.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Performed activities • Important results achieved • Cooperation with other partners • Transfer of materials/samples • (optional) Pictures showing important results (e.g. new know-generated) <p>Provide clear and measurable details.</p>
WP2	See WP1
Etc.	See WP1
1.3 Risk Management	<p>Include any change from the DoA (Annex 1 from GA) and identified risks from the reporting period.</p>
1.4 Impacts	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Describe the progress of the project so far towards delivering scientific impact,

1.5 Update of the exploitation and dissemination plan	<p>based on its objectives and towards delivering impact in any of the following fields (if applicable): scientific, economic, societal or industrial production or processes.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on changes to the expected impacts presented in your DoA (if any) and the effects on the project/need for adaptations. • Where necessary, provide further details of your monitoring and evaluation strategy, including: references to baselines, benchmarks, assumptions used (with justification) as well as calculations performed to quantify the impacts. If necessary, provide this information in a separate deliverable /a dedicated section of a deliverable.
	<p>Include any updates to the plan for exploitation and dissemination of results on your side.</p>
	<p>Explain next planned actions, incoming deliverables and milestones for the next reporting period.</p>
	<p>If access to research infrastructure has been provided under the Grant Agreement, include access provision activity, notably for Transnational Access activities and Virtual Access activities.</p> <p>If questions, you can ask the Project Coordinator and Project Manager.</p>
1.6 Plans for the next 6 months	
(Optional) 1.X Access to research infrastructure	

Please include a table explaining if and how each recommendation from previous reviews and/or Project Officer assessment has been addressed.

2. Follow-up of recommendations and comments from previous reviews

Previous recommendations 1.	If and how the recommendation from previous reviews and/or Project Officer assessment has been addressed
Etc.	See Previous recommendation 1.

3. Open Science

Open Science practices	Describe the Open Science practices related to early and open sharing of research (e.g. through pre-registration, registered reports, pre-prints or crowd-sourcing of solutions to a specific problem).
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Reproducibility

Describe the concrete measures that ensure the reproducibility of the results obtained during the action i.e., measures to ensure that the same results can be obtained by using the same data and/or methods, etc.

Explain the reasons for deviations from the DoA, the consequences and the proposed corrective actions.

4. DEVIATIONS FROM ANNEX 1 AND ANNEX 2

4.1 Tasks/objectives

Include explanations for tasks not fully implemented, critical objectives not fully achieved and/or not being on schedule. Explain also the impact on other tasks on the available resources and the planning. Explain also the impact on other tasks and provide and provide details to allow assessing whether the project is on track.

4.2 Use of resources

Explanations :

- On deviations of the use of resources between actual and planned use of resources in Annex 1, especially related to person-months per work package.
- On transfer of costs categories (if applicable).
- On adjustments to previous financial statements (if applicable).

4.2.1 Unforeseen subcontracting (if applicable)

Specify here :

- the work (the tasks) performed by a subcontractor which may cover only a limited part of the project
- explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for a subcontract, taking into account the specific characteristics of the project
- the confirmation that the subcontractor has been selected ensuring the best value for money or, if appropriate, the lowest price and avoiding any conflict of interests
- Include the name of subcontractor and amount.

4.2.2. Unforeseen use of in kind contributions

Specify here :

- the identity of the third party
- the resources made available by the third party respectively against payment or free of charges
- explanation of the circumstances which caused the need for using these resources for carrying out the work.

8.5 Appendix E: SEHRENE PERT diagrams

7.5. Appendix F: SEHRENE detailed Gantt chart

1 Milestones

